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Behavioural Orientation of Youth in Visakhapatnam: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

This article presents the socio-economic conditions, likes, dislikes, hobbies, activities and aspirations of the youth in Visakhapatnam. As we know, youth are the competent strength and asset for every nation. The ideology of youth is changing from generation to generation. The goals, hobbies, likes, dislikes and activities of the present generation of youth are different from the previous generations. This is a quantitative research study conducted at Andhra University in Visakhapatnam. The respondents are youth aged between 18-29 years pursuing their graduation and post-graduation. The study adopted a descriptive research design, purposive sampling method and selected 82 respondents from various colleges of Andhra University. The data was collected through a structured, pre-tested questionnaire shared via Google form. Analysis revealed that 43.9 per cent of the youth visit devotional places like temples and churches occasionally, followed by 39 per cent of the respondents who visit the devotional places once a week. The study found that 73.1 per cent of the respondents participate in sports regularly in the nearby playgrounds. All students have social media accounts and the majority of them are using WhatsApp, Instagram and YouTube. They are foodies and the majority (68.3%) of respondents like Biryani. Very less (6.1%) of the respondents accepted that they are obese. The majority (61%) of the respondents sleep after 11:00 pm. The majority 52.4 percent of the respondents stated that they had already fallen in love. The major career aspiration of the respondents is getting a government job (63.4%). The study suggested that the youth who have academic problems should increase their focus on their education and get guidance from the senior faculty members of their institutions.

Keywords: Career aspirations, Congenial family environment, Devotional places, Social media, Tobacco usage.

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Introduction

Nelson Mandela quoted that “The youth of today are the leaders of tomorrow”. This statement needs a serious discussion because the hobbies and aspirations of the youth are changing from generation to generation. The present generation of youth is updated and born with computers and smartphones. The present generation of youth’s aspirations and hobbies are different. As we know that youth are the backbone of every nation. The growth and development of every nation depend on the participation of youth. The National Youth Policy 2014 defined youth as persons between the ages of 15-29 years. Youth is the time of life between childhood and adulthood (Port Vila International Society, 2021). According to Census (2011), more than 50 percent of the Indian population is under the age of 29 years. India is one of the youngest countries in the world. Young people are the innovators, creators, builders and leaders of the future. There is a lot of healthy competition between youth in terms of working capacity and perseverance. The future of youth depends on their skills, health, decision-making and real choices in life (Vision IAS, 2021).

The other side of youth in India is different. Youth face various challenges related to employment, health, drug abuse, suicidal tendencies, and the adverse impact of media. Mental health problems are also increasing in Indian youth and still, it is raising (Ipshita Das, 2018). Sometimes, the attitudes and hobbies of the youth are influenced by their culture, caste, religion and peer pressure. The impact of Covid-19 also changed the goals, hobbies and aspirations of the youth. The present study is conducted to understand the present generation youth’s hobbies, likes, dislikes and aspirations. The researcher conducted a review of the literature to get a clear understanding of the topic and presented it below.

Review of Literature

Okada (2012) reported that India has complicated and tremendous hurdles in encouraging young people for skill development, including the size of the youth population. The vast majority of young people from economically and socially disadvantaged backgrounds have limited access to education and vocational training in India. Azeez et al. (2014) conducted a study on the habit of drinking alcohol among 1150 college students with the breakup of 713 females and 337 males. Out of 1150 students, 304 (26.4%) consume alcohol with the breakup of 167 (54.9%) males and 137 (45.1%) females. Most of them were social drinkers, and majority of them consumed 2-3 drinks in one sitting. Tendency of binge drinking was high.

Deb et al. (2016) contended that female students were significantly more spiritual than male students. Hindu religion and lower family income were associated with

lower spirituality. Higher spirituality was associated with a congenial family environment and more support from teachers and classmates. Naafs (2018) purported that the young people's aspirations are for employment and middle class standards of living. Faced with limited upward mobility, class as an aspirational category rather than everyday reality underpins young people's claims about the good life. Abraham & Rangarao (2019) found that 76 percent of students have social media accounts on one or two platforms. The majority (80%) of the respondents are using YouTube and 76 per cent of the respondents are using WhatsApp and thirdly 74 per net of the respondents are using Facebook. The students (82%) are using social media for chatting.

Vule and Krnjaic (2019) conducted a study to find out the correlation between certain creative activities, operationalized through hobbies and five aspects of well-being. The adolescents were engaged in the hobbies of computer programming and graphic design, which might motivate them towards possible career choices due to their popularity. Hobbies reflect adaptability and positive development among adolescents. Antarang (2019) found that the fear of unemployment is a tangible threat for the under privileged youth. Most of the respondents shared that their friends and relatives were struggling to find jobs. In addition to this are the challenges like little to no awareness of possible career avenues, half-baked understanding of what a work life or career entails and the lack of resources to overcome financial and cultural obstacles. The youth indicated interest in pursuing job-specific training for specific roles or careers through vocational, skill-development or career-development short-term courses.

Haranath (2020) observed that many students are inspired to become government employees. And one-third of respondents have no clarity on their aspirations. Parents always think about their studies and their future. It is found in this study that the majority of parents are frequently discussing with their children about their aspirations. It is understood that these studies are focussed on the skills, hobbies and opportunities for the youth. The authors have taken a particular aspect and presented their inferences e.g., youth and religion, youth and social media, youth and habits etc. There is a need to further explore the skills and aspirations of youth in India. The present study presents comprehensive information on youth skills, hobbies and aspirations.

The Rationale of the study

The youth are the competent strength of every nation. The ideology of youth is changing from generation to generation. The goals, hobbies, likes, dislikes and activities of the present generation of youth are different from the previous generation. The youth of the current generation are hard workers, born in the computer era, and have

more technical and soft skills. Another side of this generation of youth is laziness, free association with the opposite sex, addicted to social media and smartphones. Health problems are also increasing among this generation of youth in India. These youth have different career aspirations and goals to get success in their lives. The youth need directions and inspiration to mould their hobbies, goals and aspirations. Previously, a few studies were conducted to understand the hobbies, likes, dislikes and aspirations of the educated youth but those studies were conducted in developed countries and other states of India. In this connection, the present study is proposed to conduct a study to understand the ideology, likes, and dislikes of the present generation youth of Visakhapatnam. This study was conducted on the youth aged between 18-29 years living in Visakhapatnam.

The Objectives of the study

- To study the socio- demographic profile of the youth living in Visakhapatnam
- To understand the behavioural orientation of youth living in Visakhapatnam city in terms of their habits, likes and dislikes, and career aspirations.
- To offer appropriate suggestions for the development of ideology amongst youth

Method

Study Area: The present study was conducted on the students enrolled with Andhra University in Visakhapatnam to understand their hobbies and aspirations. Visakhapatnam is the biggest educational hub of Andhra Pradesh and has been declared as a smart city. It is also one of the biggest cities of Andhra Pradesh. Andhra University was established 96 years back.

Research Design: This study adopted quantitative research approach to arrive at the results. Research design is a blueprint for any research study and it provides the layout to conduct a study. This study adopted a descriptive research design to describe, analyse and present the views of the respondents.

Sampling: This study adopted the purposive sampling technique from the non-probability sampling method. The study selected 82 students from the College of Arts and Commerce, Science and Technology and College of Engineering of Andhra University. There were four students from foreign countries also.

Data Collection and Analysis: The data was collected by administering a structured, pre-tested questionnaire which was shared via Google form. It has 25 questions with

multiple choices. The data was collected in November and December 2021, and was analysed through Ms-Excel 2010 version and SPSS 20 version.

Results and Discussion

Age is an important independent variable in any research study. It is calculated by completed years of life of the respondents. This study selected respondents between the ages of 18-29 years. Based on age, the respondents were divided into four groups for the present study. Table 1 presents socio-economic background of the respondents.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Background of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
AGE		
18-20	10	12.2
21-23	34	41.5
24-26	27	32.9
27 and above	11	13.4
Total	82	100.0
Mean Age: 23.45	Median: 23.00	Mode: 25:00
Chi-square: 22.390	df: 3	Significance: 0.000
SEX		
Male	52	63.4
Female	30	36.6
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 5.902	df: 1	Significance: 0.015
EDUCATION		
Below graduation	4	4.9
Graduation	43	52.4
Post-graduation	35	42.7
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 31.049	df: 2	Significance: 0.000

COLLEGE		
Arts College	39	47.6
Science College	29	35.4
Engineering College	5	6.1
Other Colleges	9	11.0
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 37.512	df: 3	Significance: 0.000
INCOME OF THE FAMILY		
Below poverty line	65	79.3
Above poverty line	17	20.7
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 28.098	df: 1	Significance: 0.000

It is clear from the table that 41.5 percent, 32.9 percent, 13.4 percent and 12.2 percent of the respondents belonged to the age groups of 21-23 years, 24-26 years, 27 and above years, and 18-20 years respectively. The majority of the respondents were males (63.4%) in comparison to females (36.6%). Most of the respondents were pursuing graduation (52.4 %), while others were pursuing post-graduation (42.7%) and below graduation programs (4.9 %). Out of the total sample of 82 participants, 47.6 percent, 35.4 percent, 6.1 percent and 11.0 percent were from Arts College, Science College, Engineering College and Other Colleges of Visakhapatnam respectively.

Income refers to earning money in a particular period i.e., per month/ per year. The people receive income in exchange for work, while producing a product or service, or investing capital. In India, the families were broadly divided into two types based on their income i.e., below poverty line families and above poverty line families. Below poverty line families are poor families. The data in the above table shows that among 82 participants, the majority (79.3%) of the respondents were below poverty line, while remaining respondents (20.7%) were above poverty line. Andhra University is a state public institution and tuition fees is less in comparison to private institutions. The students from poor and middle-class families work hard to get admission in Andhra University.

Sleeping time

The American Academy of Sleep Medicine has recommended that teenagers aged 13–18 years should sleep 8–10 hours per day. Centre for Disease Control and Prevention

(2022) found that teenagers aged 13 to 18 years who reported sleeping less than 8 hours were also considered not getting enough sleep. With this background, Table 2 presents the sleeping timings of the respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents by their Sleeping Time

Average Sleeping time	Frequency	Percentage
9 pm	5	6.1
10 pm	28	34.1
11 pm	36	43.9
12 o'clock & afterwards	13	15.9
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 27.561	Df: 3	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table revealed that 43.9 percent of the respondents stated that they sleep after 11:00 pm, followed by 34.1 percent of the respondents who stated that they sleep after 10:00 pm and 15.9 percent of the respondents stated that they sleep after 12:00 midnight and afterwards. The reason may be that students sit after dinner and share their joys, and information for hours together. The discussion is informative and has entertainment. The study is in line with the findings of Graham (2000) and Hariharan (2022). Makkar (2022) had observed that 59 percent of India goes to bed past the ideal bedtime of 11 pm. Zeek et al. (2015) and Alfonsi et al. (2020) reported that majority of the youth are sleeping after 11:00pm. *Almost half (47.8%)* felt daytime sleepiness almost every day.

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by their age and sleeping time

Age	Sleeping time				Total
	9:00 pm	10:00 pm	11:00 pm	12 o'clock & afterwards	
18-20	1	6	3	0	10
21-23	1	13	16	4	34
24-26	2	8	16	2	28
27 and above	1	1	1	7	10
Total	5	28	36	13	82
Chi-Square Value: 31.222		df: 9		Significance: 0.000	

Analysis of the data on Age and Sleeping time are cross-tabulated and the results show that there is an association between two variables as it is evident that the students who are lower in age are sleeping early than the youth who are higher in age (Significant at 0.000).

Participation in devotional activities

Devotional activities increase the mental strength of individuals. It has been observed that nowadays the participation of youth has increased in devotional activities. Table 4 presents the details of participation of youth in the devotional and prayer activities.

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by their participation in devotional activities

Devotional activities	Frequency	Percentage
Once or twice in a week	14	17.1
Once in a Month	32	39.0
Occasionally	36	43.9
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 10.049	df: 2	Significance: 0.007

The data in the table revealed that 43.9 percent of the youth attend devotional places i.e., temples and churches occasionally, followed by 39 percent of the respondents who attend the devotional places once a week and 17.1 percent of respondents attend the devotional places once or twice in a week. Similar findings were reported by Kanwal (2019), who had observed that 22 percent of the youth from the metro cities went to places of worship once a week, whereas 20 percent of the young people from non-metro cities visited religious places once a week. This study is in line with the study of Rathore (2023), who reported that 22 percent of the youth from the metro cities went to places of worship once a week in 2019 across India. The study is in line with the study of Deb et al. (2016) who concluded that female students are significantly more spiritual than male students.

Participation in Sports

Sports refers to the physical activities that are performed during leisure time. Sports are of two types i.e., indoor and outdoor. The games that are played in an outside or open space are outdoor sports and the games that are played inside are indoor sports. After Covid-19, it appears that interest of the students has increased in sports to

improve their health status. Table 5 presents the information about the participation of youth in sports.

Table 5: Distribution of the respondents by their participation in Sports

Participation in Sports	Frequency	Percentage
Regular Participation	22	26.8
Irregular Participation	38	46.3
No Participation	22	26.8
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 6.244	df: 2	Significance: 0.044

The data shows that among 82 participants, most of them participate in sports (73.1%) while only 26.8 percent do not participate in sports. It reveals that among those who participate in sports, most of them participate irregularly (46.3%), and 26.8 percent participate regularly. The study is in line with the work of Black Li et al. (2022) who reported that children and adolescents in the South were less likely to participate in sports (48.7%) as compared with all other regions of the country. The reason may be that most of the youth focus on the competitive exams to get a government job.

The study also found that the majority (53.4%) of the respondents participate in both indoor as well as outdoor games, and 33.3 percent of the respondents participate in outdoor games only, and few of them (9.8) participate in indoor sports only. The reason may be that Andhra University has very good play grounds and an indoor stadium. The results are in line with the study of Bharatan (2023), who reported that *outdoor games* provide the youth the opportunity for much-needed exercises, and also help them to learn basic life skills such as teamwork and strategy. The findings of a study undertaken by The Times of India (2019), revealed that almost 64 percent of Indians say that they don't exercise.

Social Media

Social Media is an internet-based form of communication. There are many forms of social media, including blogs, micro blogs, wikis, social networking sites, photo sharing sites, instant messaging, video sharing sites, podcasts, widgets, virtual worlds, and more. The present generation of youth is very familiar with social media. Figure 1 presents the details of participation of youth on social media platforms.

Figure 1: Distribution of the respondents by their participation in Social Media

The data in the figure shows that among 82 participants, the majority (29) of the respondents like to use WhatsApp, while 27 respondents are interested in using YouTube, followed by 18 respondents using Instagram and only 8 respondents like Facebook. It is observed that the present generation of youth is using WhatsApp, YouTube and Instagram. Comparatively, less people are using Facebook. The students use these social media platforms to share their events and happy moments with their friends. Very less people share pictures related to social problems and politics. The results are in line with the study of Abraham & Rangarao (2019); Vogels et al. (2022) reported that majority of the youth are using YouTube and WhatsApp, and thirdly Facebook. But in this study the users of Facebook are less than the users of Instagram. TikTok was another favourite social media for youth of India, but it was banned by the Government of India.

Food

Without food, there is no life. There are so many dishes available in today's world. Some people like Indian foods like Biryani, Thali, Phulka/Chapathi, Pav Bhaji, Pani Puri etc. whereas others like western foods like Pizza, Burger, Noodles etc. Among the variety of food items, everyone has his or her favourites. Table 6 presents the favourite dishes of the youth.

Table 6: Distribution of the respondents by their Favourite Food

Favourite Food	Frequency	Percentage
Biryani	56	68.3
Thali/Meals with rice	18	22.0
Phulka / Chapathi	8	9.8
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 46.927	df: 2	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table shows that among 82 participants, the majority (68.3%) of respondents like Biryani, while 22.0 percent of the respondents like Thali/Meals with rice, and only 9.8 percent of the respondents like Phulka/Chapathi. Nowadays, the youth are very much interested to eat Biryani. Both vegetarians and non-vegetarians Biryanies are available in restaurants in different varieties. When students organize birthday parties and some other celebrations, they offer Biryani to their fellow students in restaurants. The findings are in line with the study of Joshi (2019); Deb (2020) reported that Biryani is the most ordered food in India, because it is a hassle-free meal, easy to serve, easy to heat up, and sufficient for two young people.

Obesity among youth

Obesity is a chronic condition defined by an excess amount of body fat. It indicates the weight greater than what is considered healthy. Obesity has been more precisely defined by the National Institute of Health (NIH) as BMI (Body Mass Index) of 30 and above. Sometimes, it may be the cause of malnutrition also. Table 7 presents the perception of students about their obesity.

Table7: Distribution of the respondents by their Obesity

Obesity	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	5	6.1
No	69	84.1
Don't Know	8	9.8
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 95.439	Df: 2	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table shows that among 82 participants, the majority (84.1%) of respondents perceived that they are not Obese, while 6.1 percent of respondents

perceived that they are Obese and 9.8 percent of respondents did not know about their Obesity status. Shanmugapriya et al. (2016) reported that the prevalence of obesity and overweight was 15.8 percent among urban and 26 percent among the rural youth in India. The results of the present study are in contrast with the research investigation of Das (2022), who reported that obesity has increased at national level from 21 percent to 24 percent among women, and from 19 percent to 23 percent among men. In this study, the percentage of obese persons is less, may be, because figures are based on the perception of respondents and not on the basis of actual measurement of BMI.

The reason for the majority of the respondents not perceiving themselves as obese in this study may also be due to the fact that most of the students came from rural areas and they were likely to have done physical work on their agricultural farms. The results are also in contrast with the study of International Institute for Population Sciences (2007), because as per NFHS-3 data of 2005-2006 the overweights among girls and boys were 2.4 percent and 31.7 percent respectively. It may be so because data pertains to an old study conducted in 2007.

Falling in Love

Falling in love is one of the great experiences in every human being's life. It means to get attracted to someone of the opposite sex and begin to love him/her. This generation of youth is very fast and they fall in love easily. Previous generations lived and loved in offline mode and the present is living and loving in online mode. This love builds good relationships which lead to marriage. The present generation of youth get attached or detached easily. Table 8 presents the status of falling in love amongst the respondents.

Table 8: Distribution of the respondents by their status of falling in Love

Falling in Love	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	43	52.4
No	38	46.3
Love with mom and dad	1	1.2
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 38.512	df: 2	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table shows that 52.4 percent of the respondents stated that they had already fallen in love, followed by 46.3 percent of the respondents who stated that

they had not fallen in love till then. Interestingly, 1.2 percent stated that they are in love with their mom and dad. The present generation of youth are very fast and have the freedom to communicate anything to their fellow mates. Boren (2015) survey says that men fall in love more times than women and nearly half of women fell in love once only. The study found that among 43 respondents, 74.4 percent of the respondents stated that their love was on both the sides and 25.6 percent of the respondents stated that their love was on one side only.

Table 9: Distribution of the respondents by their Sex and status of falling in love

Sex	Fell in love			Total
	Yes	No	Love with parents	
Male	32	20	0	52
Female	11	18	1	30
Total	43	38	1	82
Chi-Square: 5.88		df: 2		Significance.053

Analysis of the cross-tabulated data on Sex and status of falling in love has revealed that there is an association between the two variables as it is evident that more male students fall in love than female students (Significantat 0.53).

According to the Cambridge dictionary, marriage is a legally accepted relationship between two people who live together after marriage. It is an official ceremony to bind two people to live their life together happily.

Table 10: Distribution of the respondents by their interest to marry those whom they love

Are you going to marry	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	18	41.9
No	9	20.9
Don't know	16	37.2
Total	43	100.0
Chi-square: 24.439	df: 3	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table reveals that 41.9 percent of the respondents stated that they shall get married to those whom they love, while 20.9 percent of the respondents stated

that they may not get married to those whom they loved and 37.2 percent of the respondents stated that they don't know where they would get married. The results of a study by Marwaha (2021) had indicated that millennials prefer arranged marriages instead of falling in love. A study of Livemint (2018) reported that only 3 percent of young people in India go for love marriage outside of their caste or religion. A study by Keelery (2023) reported that 80 percent of the youth preferred to get married to their partners in 2019. Only 15 percent are interested in live-in relationship and love.

Alcohol usage

It means drinking any type of alcohol continuously. Alcoholism is not a recognized diagnostic entity. Predominant diagnostic classifications are alcohol use disorder or alcohol dependence. Alcoholism is also one of the root causes of mental or physical health problems. The present generation of youth is very familiar with alcohol. Table 11 presents the details on the habit of alcohol use amongst the respondents.

Table 11: Distribution of the respondents by their participation in Alcohol usage

Habit of Alcohol usage	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	14	17.1
No	68	82.9
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 35.561	Df: 1	Significance: 0.000

The results show that among 82 participants, the majority (82.9%) of the respondents are not habitual to drinking alcohol, while 17.1 percent of the respondents are habitual to drinking alcohol. The Community Against Drunken Driving (2019) had reported that nearly 23 percent consume alcohol even before they reached the age of 18. In fact, many of them consumed alcohol without disclosing it to their families. In contrast, a study by Press Trust of India (2022) had reported that 75 percent youth consume alcohol before turning 21 years. The percentage was found to be very high, may be due to the fact that the study was conducted in metropolitan cities.

Table 12: Distribution of the respondents by their Age and Alcohol usage

Age	Drinking alcohol		Total
	Yes	No	
18-20	0	10	10
21-23	2	32	34
24-26	8	20	28
27 and above	4	6	10
Total	14	68	82
Chi-Square Value: 11.393	df: 3	Significance: 0.010	

Analysis of the cross-tabulated data on Age and alcohol usage showed that there is an association between the two variables. It is evident that the lower age group students do not drink alcohol, whereas the higher age group students drink alcohol (Significant at 0.010).

Table 13: Distribution of the respondents by their sex and Alcohol usage

Sex	Drinking of alcohol		Total
	Yes	No	
Male	12	40	52
Female	2	28	30
Total	14	68	82
Pearson Chi-Square Value: 3.619(b)	df: 1	Significance: 0.057	

Analysis of the cross-tabulated data on sex and drinking of alcohol showed that there is an association between the two variables, as it is evident that more male students drink alcohol than female students (Significant at 0.057). This study is in line with the study of Azeez et al. (2014) who reported that out of 1150 students, 304 (26.4%) consumed alcohol, and 167 (54.9%) were males and 137 (45.1%) were females. But in Azeez et al. (2014) study, the female drinkers are very high, which may be so because research work was conducted on medical college students of a metropolitan city.

Tobacco usage

It may be defined as any habitual use of tobacco leaves and their products. The predominant use of tobacco is by smoke inhalation of cigarettes, pipes, and cigars.

Smokeless tobacco refers to a variety of tobacco products that are sniffed, sucked, or chewed e.g., gutka, khaini and zarda (Al-Ibrahim & Gross, 2022). Cigarette smoking and tobacco usage lead to chronic diseases, including cancer. Tobacco contains Nicotine, which may result in addiction to its products. Table 14 presents the details of tobacco usage among the youth.

Table 14: Distribution of the respondents by their Habit of Tobacco usage

Habit of Tobacco usage	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	3	3.7
No	79	96.3
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 700.439	df: 1	Significance: 0.000

The findings reveal that 96.3 per cent of the respondents do not have the habit of tobacco usage and only 3.7 per cent of the respondents have the habit of tobacco usage. The study is in contrast with the national average of tobacco smoking. Among adults (age 15+), 28.6 percent of the population currently uses tobacco products (men 42.4%; women 14.2%) in India, which is now declining (World Health Organisation, 2017).

Drug usage is a broad term that refers to the use of any substance, i.e., illegal drugs, prescribed drugs, marijuana, cocaine, heroin, inhalant, narcotics and cannabis in excessive amounts. Nowadays, drug abuse is one of the burning problems in India (Haranath & Abraham, 2022). Table 15 presents the details of the habit of drug usage among respondents.

Table 15: Distribution of the respondents by their Habit of Drugs usage

Habit of Drugs usage	Frequency	Percentage
Details	2	2.4
No	80	97.6
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 74.195	df: 1	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table revealed that 97.6 percent of the respondents do not have the habit of drug usage, while 2.4 per cent of the respondents have the habit of usage of drugs. The reason for low tobacco usage may be the higher level of awareness created by the government and social organisations to educate the youth on drug addiction.

Tsering, Pal & Dasgupta (2010), in a study, had reported that 12.5 percent of the respondents used or abused any one of the substances irrespective of time and frequency in lifetime. The results of the present study are in contrast with the study of The Economic Times (2022) which reported that there has been 50 percent rise in the number of youngsters taking mind-altering substances since 2021.

Career Aspirations of youth

The youth have a lot of career aspirations based on their education, experience and inspiration of the neighbours. They work hard to achieve their aspirations. Table 16 presents the aspirations of the respondents.

Table 16: Distribution of the respondents by their Career Aspirations

Career Aspiration	Frequency	Percentage
Software Job	11	13.4
Government Job	52	63.4
Business	4	4.9
Any Private Job	15	18.3
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 67.561	df: 3	Significance: 0.000

The data revealed that 63.4 percent of the respondents are looking for a Government job, followed by 18.3 percent of the respondents who have no specific goal/aspiration about their career and are looking for any private job. Out of the total sample of 82, 13.4 percent of the respondents have the aspiration to become software engineers and 4.9 percent of the respondents have a desire to become business persons. The people who opted for the government job are looking for jobs in various sectors i.e., banking, teaching, defence, police, navy, railways, and group 1 category jobs. The study is in line with the study of Antarang (2019) and Haranath (2020) who reported that the youth from privileged background are moving away from the government jobs and planning entrepreneurship, but the youth from poor background are interested in government jobs, and very less people are interested in entrepreneurship. Vule & Krnjaic (2019) had reported that adolescents were engaged in the hobbies of computer programming and graphic design. In the present study, it is observed that the youth are giving more priority to the government jobs in comparison to the software jobs. Table 17 presents the details of who provides career guidance regularly to the respondents.

Table 17: Distribution of the respondents by Career Guidance providers

Career guidance provider	Frequency	Percentage
Self	19	23.2
Parents and family members	36	43.9
Relatives	7	8.5
Friends	4	4.9
Teachers	12	14.6
None	4	4.9
Total	82	100.0
Chi-square: 55.707	df: 5	Significance: 0.000

The data in the table reveals that 43.9 percent of the respondents stated that career guidance is provided by their parents and family members i.e., brother/sister, followed by 23.2 percent of the respondents who stated that they are self-motivators regarding their career guidance, and 14.6 percent of the respondents stated that teachers guide them for making a career choice.

Conclusion

Overall, this study presented the socio-economic conditions, likes, dislikes, hobbies and aspirations of the students representing youth. This generation of young people is technology-friendly, and most of them are using social media, i.e., WhatsApp and Instagram regularly. It is observed that they go to sleep in the late night. The majority of the youth had already fallen in love and were interested in getting married to the same person. It is interesting to note that many students reported that they were not habitual of using alcohol, smoking, drugs and chewing tobacco products. The aspirations of the youth are that they want to become government employees.

Limitations of the study

This study was conducted on the educated young population only. The reported hobbies, likes, dislikes and aspirations belong to these students only. This study was conducted at Andhra University, Visakhapatnam and the hobbies, likes and dislikes pertaining to the students of Andhra University only. This study adopted the non-probability sampling method i.e., purposive sampling method. In view of sample restricted to Visakhapatnam city only, the results of the study cannot be generalised for the whole country.

Implications

Based on results of the study, the following suggestions and implications have been drawn:

1. The youth should follow traditional food habits rather than eating junk food.
2. The youth who are having obesity should increase the habit of walking and exercise. They should change their regular lifestyle. Yoga and meditation may help them in reducing their obesity.
3. The youth should actively participate in the sports to improve their health status. Government departments and NGOs should promote competitions amongst youth.
4. The youth who have academic problems should increase their focus on their education and get guidance from the senior faculty members to reduce their academic problems
5. Government departments and NGOs should organise the life skills education programmes for the youth.
6. Before falling in love or engaging in live-in relationship, the background of the partner should be well understood. There is a chance of getting trapped in human trafficking through the channel of love.
7. Counselling facilities should be provided to the youth who are addicted to alcohol, tobacco and other drugs by the NGOs and concerned government departments.
8. The students should participate in career upgradation programmes like spoken English, computer training, attending library, getting coaching etc. during their college days. These are helpful to the students to accomplish their aspirations.
9. The youth should interact with their parents and teachers to reduce the severity of the barriers to their career aspirations.
10. The government of Andhra Pradesh and the Government of India should introduce more schemes for the welfare of the students. The students or youth should be aware of the government schemes and should also have access to them at the appropriate time to overcome the hurdles in achieving their career goals.

11. The study needs to be replicated on a larger representative sample with diverse background. The students enrolled with private universities should also be included in the study.

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